

Evaluation Guidelines for Assessing Students' Achievement of Fashion Illustration Objectives within the Clothing and Textiles Programme

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Abstract: The major purpose of the study was to determine evaluation guidelines for assessing students' achievement of the fashion illustration objectives within the Clothing and Textiles Programme in Universities in Nigeria. The population and sample for the study were made up of eight hundred and fifty-nine (859) respondents comprising 46 Home Economics lecturers, 8 Fine Arts lecturers and 805 registered professional garment manufacturers in areas under study were purposely selected. Data for the research was collected using the Fashion Illustration Curriculum Needs Assessment Questionnaire (overall coefficient = 0.984). The findings of the study showed that the 26 evaluation guidelines determined in the study were adequate for assessing achievement of fashion illustration objectives. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that Curriculum planners (National Universities Commission) and administrators should utilize the evaluation guidelines of fashion illustration developed in this study in their review of the current Home Economics programmes in universities in Nigeria such that their challenging curriculum will prepare students for realistic employment. Therefore, the research study if adopted by benchmark will address curriculum issues. It is necessary to re-train the abilities of lecturers of Home Economics in fashion illustration to enable them to prepare their students for the challenges in the workforce.

Keywords: Curriculum, Fashion Illustration, Evaluation guidelines, Home Economics, Nigerian Universities, Students' achievement

1. Introduction

Curriculum development can be defined as ‘the systematic planning of what is taught and learned in schools as reflected in courses of study and school programmes’ (Osuji, 2017). Stages in curriculum development as highlighted by Tyler (1975) are selection of aims, goals and objectives, selection of learning experiences and content, organization of learning experiences, and evaluation of the extent which the objectives have been achieved. Occupational Home Economics curriculum is planned and developed on the basis of knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for successful employment in particular jobs. Hence, self-reliance and income generation activities are stressed in the study of Clothing and Textiles. Although, the curriculum for Clothing and Textiles programmes of universities in Nigeria provide for teaching and learning of some theoretical and practical skills, however, fashion illustration which is a basic requirement for competency in garment designing, pattern drafting, alteration, grading and clothing construction is lacking in the NUC curriculum in Home Economics.

Fashion illustration is the communication of fashion that is anchored on illustration, drawing and painting. Fashion illustration is a form of stylized drawing; it seeks to communicate not only an artistic representation, but a sense of style. It is usually commissioned for reproduction in fashion magazine as one part of an editorial feature or for the purpose of advertising and promoting fashion makers, fashion boutiques and department stores (Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009). Fashion illustrations appear on the internet, greeting cards, product packaging and branded merchandise in magazines, catalog and trade journals (Wolfe, 1993; Weber, 1990; Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009). Fashion illustration is considered as the most fundamental component of fashion design. It is used to present the design ideas. Fashion illustration can be presented through many forms and textures with a lot of creative themes and impressions. The fashion design business is the major focus of fashion illustration. Fashion illustration has a major role in the presentation, communication and marketing of designs (White, N., & Griffiths, I. (2000). Mckelvey (2006) stated that fashion illustration is used widely in the industry, by fashion prediction companies, by designers, by large fashion companies, creating ranges, by fashion magazines and trade journals, and by students.

Fashion illustration is an important area of Clothing and Textiles programme in institutions. Several authors like Wolfe (1993), Weber (1990), and Mckelvey and Munslow (2009) explained that the very base of clothing designing, pattern drafting, alteration, grading and clothing construction is illustration. Components of fashion illustration include: drawing human figure (including heads, hands, faces and feet); drawing clothing for different individuals and purposes as well as accessories such as shoes, boots and hand bags; creation of textures in clothing to indicate different fabrics and development of skills in creativity necessary for entrepreneurship. Fashion illustration needs to be taught along with other components of Clothing and Textiles. This in turns requires appropriate curriculum.

Fashion illustration courses are the basis of clothing designing, pattern drafting, alteration, grading, and clothing construction. Its absence in the Clothing and Textiles NUC curriculum of Home Economics programmes in Nigerian universities is a major deficiency (National Universities Commission (NUC), 2007). Therefore, fashion illustration courses are not offered by the students as observed by the researcher. Thus, students and graduates of Home Economics are not adequately equipped with knowledge and skills needed for drawing

human figure as well as garment styles. Also, students lack knowledge and skill in communication of fashion which originates with illustration, drawing and painting. In this regard, students and graduates of Home Economics are not adequately equipped with skills needed for manufacturing and marketing of Clothing, Textiles and accessories.

This study on the development of Fashion Illustration Curriculum for integration into Clothing and Textiles programmes of Home Economics Education in universities in Nigeria will form basis for training students and graduates of textiles and clothing in creativity, technical, and entrepreneurship skills necessary for self-employment and wealth creation. Integrating Fashion Illustration Curriculum into Clothing and Textiles programmes of Home Economics Education is a measure towards improving the clothing and accessories produced in the fashion industry necessary for economic development in Nigeria.

1.1. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine evaluation guidelines for assessing students' achievement of the fashion illustration objectives within the Clothing and Textiles Programme in Universities in Nigeria.

Specifically, the study:

- (a) identified the mean responses of Home Economics lecturers, Fine and Applied Arts lecturers, and Clothing production experts in industries on the evaluation techniques that could be used for assessing students' achievement of the Fashion Illustration objectives within the Clothing and Textiles programme in universities in Nigeria;
- (b) determined differences in the mean responses of Home Economics lecturers, Fine and Applied Arts lecturers, and Clothing production experts in industries on the evaluation techniques that could be used for assessing students' achievement of the Fashion Illustration objectives within the Clothing and Textiles programme in universities in Nigeria;

1.2. Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There are no significant differences in the mean responses of Home Economics lecturers, Fine and Applied Arts lecturers, and Clothing production experts in industries on the evaluation activities that could be adopted for assessing the students' achievement of objectives of Fashion Illustration within the Clothing and Textiles programme of universities in Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The research design that was utilized for this study is the Research and Development (R & D) methodology. It has shown that Research and Development is an industry-based development model in which the findings of research are used to design new products and procedures, which then are systematically field-tested, validated and refined until they meet specified criteria of effectiveness, quality, or similar standards.

The Research and Development design was considered adequate because a prototype

was developed which is the main crux of the Research and Development. In addition to this, the study developed a new product (Fashion Illustration Curriculum) which was field tested on Home Economics students, validated by experts and revised. The systems approach model is a widely used model of educational research and development.

2.2. Area of the Study

The research was carried out in three geo-political zones in Nigeria namely, South East, South West and North Central. There are five states in South East, Nigeria namely, Abia, Imo, Anambra, Enugu and Ebonyi states. The study was conducted in four out of the five states in South-East, Nigeria where Home Economics is studied at the degree level. The universities in the study area where Home Economics is taught were purposely selected for the study. They are Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, (MOUUAU) in Abia State, University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) in Enugu State; Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, (EBSU) in Ebonyi State and Abia State University, Umuahia Campus (ABSU) in Abia State. In South West, the study was carried out in University of Lagos, Lagos State. In North Central, the study was conducted in University of Agriculture, Makurdi, in Benue state and Kogi State University, Kogi.

The study was conducted among the clothing manufacturers in the major commercial town in each of the states that was used for the study. In Abia State, the study was conducted in Aba. In Enugu State, the study was undertaken in Enugu while in Ebonyi State the study was conducted in Abakaliki. In South West, the study was carried out in Lagos state. In North Central, the study was carried out in Makurdi in Benue State as well as in Ayangba in Kogi state.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for the study was made up of 859 respondents comprising 46 Home Economics lecturers, 8 Fine and Applied Arts lecturers who study textiles and fashion in their curriculum and 805 clothing production experts in industries.

2.3.1. Sample and Sampling Technique:

The total number of respondents for this study was eight hundred and fifty nine respondents comprising of forty six Home Economics lecturers, eight Fine and Applied Arts lecturers, and eight hundred and five clothing production experts.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Data for the research was collected using the evaluation guidelines of Fashion Illustration Curriculum Needs Assessment Questionnaire (FICNAQ) designed by the researcher in response to the evaluation guidelines that could be adopted for assessing the achievement of the objectives of the fashion illustration in universities in Nigeria study. It was made up of a four-point rating scale. The four - point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree were used for the study. Values of 4,3,2,1 representing strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree respectively were assigned to the scale.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data for the research questions were answered using Means Scores. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 17.0.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean scores of responses of Home Economics Lecturers, Fine Arts Lecturers, Final Year Home Economics students, Clothing Production Experts on the Guidelines for Assessing the Achievement of Objectives of Fashion Illustration (FICNAQ) curriculum of Clothing and Textiles programmes of universities in Nigeria.

S/N	Guidelines for Assessing the Achievement of Objectives of fashion illustration	\bar{X}	SD	REMARKS	Page 396
	At the end of fashion illustration education students should be able to :				
1	Explain the concept of fashion illustration	3.60	0.52	Agreed	
2	Explain fashion terminologies	3.55	0.53	Agreed	
3	Explain the elements of design and their use in fashion illustration	3.69	1.10	Agreed	
4	Explain the principles of design and their use in fashion illustration	3.63	1.36	Agreed	
5	Describe eight different common figure types	3.43	0.59	Agreed	
6	Describe four basic shapes (silhouettes) that are used in clothing	3.62	0.52	Agreed	
7	Identify and use various drawing media for fashion illustration	3.45	0.61	Agreed	
8	Identify and use various colouring media for fashion illustration	3.47	0.65	Agreed	
9	Describe four different fashion illustration techniques	3.53	0.56	Agreed	
10	Sketch a female and a male croquis using the specific proportions of the fashion, figure and the grid.	3.53	0.56	Agreed	
11	Draw children in different locations	3.53	0.56	Agreed	
12	Draw women's proportions and body shape, the female face, female poses, female clothing, female fashion figure proportions.	3.49	0.59	Agreed	
13	Draw men's proportions and body shape, the male face, male poses, male clothing, male fashion figure proportion.	3.42	0.66	Agreed	
14	Analyze three common drawing problems	3.54	0.57	Agreed	
15	Develop two free hand design projects for presentation	3.59	0.55	Agreed	
16	Draw any four different clothing designs and accessories for promotion	3.52	0.61	Agreed	
17	Draw any five different clothing designs and accessories for manufacture	3.51	0.58	Agreed	
18	Produce any two fashion illustration articles for advertising and education	3.50	0.61	Agreed	
19	Draw two different clothing designs onto fashion figure templates	3.56	0.54	Agreed	
20	Draw two different clothing designs onto figure templates	3.53	0.57	Agreed	
21	Draw two different designs of each of the following: dresses, skirts, tops, pants and jackets	3.64	0.53	Agreed	
22	Draw three different designs of each of the following accessories	3.46	0.60	Agreed	

	- hats, handbags, shoes, and boots			
23	Draw four different jewelries (necklaces, bangles, earrings)	3.47	0.60	Agreed
24	Identify design portfolios, contents and layout	3.46	0.66	Agreed
25	Plan and execute a design presentation	3.35	0.80	Agreed
26	Evaluate design presentations	3.47	0.64	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.52	0.64	Agreed

Key: N1= 46 Home Economics lecturers; N2= 8 Fine and Applied Arts lecturers; N3=805 Clothing production experts

SD= Standard Deviation

Total respondents = 859; XG= Grand mean = 3.52

F is significant at Sig of F \leq 0.05, F value= ANOVA

The result in Table 1 shows a mean analysis of items 1-26 (Mean =3.52, SD = 0.64) which shows that the respondents agreed on what should constitute the guidelines for assessing achievement of fashion illustration objectives. Twenty-six items were shown in the table. All the items had means within 3.35-3.69 were agreed by the respondents as guidelines for assessing the achievement of objectives of fashion illustration.

The Standard Deviation of most of the guidelines for assessing the achievement of objectives of fashion illustration is less than 1.00 (with the exception of items 3 and 4). This indicates that the responses obtained by the respondents were not far from one another and also not far from the mean. Therefore, the mean values can be regarded as valid.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of responses of Home Economics Lecturers, Fine Arts Lecturers, Final Year Home Economics students, Clothing Production Experts on the Guidelines for Assessing the Achievement of Objectives of Fashion Illustration (FICNAQ) curriculum of Clothing and Textiles programmes of universities in Nigeria.

S/N	Guidelines for Assessing the Achievement of Objectives of fashion illustration	\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_3	SD ₃	XG	SD	F-value	Sig. of F	REMARKS
At the end of fashion illustration education students should be able to :												
1	Explain the concept of fashion illustration	3.62	0.49	3.75	0.46	3.58	0.53	3.58	0.52	0.50	0.60	NS
2	Explain fashion terminologies	3.54	0.50	3.50	0.53	3.52	0.54	3.52	0.54	0.04	0.96	NS
3	Explain the elements of	3.63	0.53	3.87	0.35	3.68	0.20	3.68	1.17	0.15	0.85	NS

4	design and their use in fashion illustration Explain the principles of design and their use in fashion illustration	3.62	0.53	3.87	0.35	3.62	1.48	3.62	1.44	0.11	0.88	NS
5	Describe eight different common figure types	3.39	0.53	3.62	0.74	3.41	0.58	3.41	0.58	0.55	0.57	NS
6	Describe four basic shapes (silhouettes) that are used in clothing	3.60	0.53	3.75	0.46	3.60	0.53	3.60	0.53	0.31	0.72	NS
7	Identify and use various drawing media for fashion illustration	3.43	0.62	3.62	0.51	3.43	0.62	3.43	0.61	0.38	0.68	NS
8	Identify and use various colouring media for fashion illustration	3.50	0.54	3.62	0.51	3.44	0.67	3.45	0.66	0.40	0.67	NS
9	Describe four different fashion illustration techniques	3.48	0.54	3.50	0.53	3.52	0.55	3.52	0.55	0.10	0.89	NS
10	Sketch a female and a male croquis using the specific proportions of the fashion, figure and the	3.56	0.58	3.50	0.53	3.51	0.56	3.51	0.56	0.20	0.81	NS

11	grid. Draw children in different locations	3.45	0.58	3.62	0.51	3.41	0.66	3.41	0.66	0.51	0.60	NS
12	Draw women's proportions and body shape, the female face, female poses, female clothing, female fashion figure proportions.	3.54	0.58	3.50	0.53	3.47	0.59	3.48	0.59	0.27	0.76	NS
13	Draw men's proportions and body shape, the male face, male poses, male clothing, male fashion figure proportion.	3.41	0.58	3.62	0.51	3.40	0.67	3.40	0.67	0.44	0.63	NS
14	Analyze three common drawing problems	3.47	0.58	3.62	0.51	3.52	0.57	3.52	0.57	0.28	0.75	NS
15	Develop two free hand design projects for presentation	3.58	0.49	3.62	0.51	3.57	0.55	3.57	0.55	0.04	0.95	NS
16	Draw any four different clothing designs and accessories for promotion	3.58	0.49	3.62	0.51	3.49	0.62	3.50	0.61	0.60	0.54	NS
17	Draw any five different clothing	3.56	0.50	3.75	0.46	3.49	0.59	3.50	0.58	0.97	0.37	S

18	designs and accessories for manufacture	Produce any two fashion illustration articles for advertising and education	3.54	0.50	3.62	0.51	3.51	0.61	3.51	0.60	0.20	0.81	NS
19	Draw two different clothing designs onto fashion figure templates	Draw two different clothing designs onto figure templates	3.56	0.54	3.62	0.51	3.49	0.58	3.50	0.57	0.46	0.62	NS
20	Draw two different clothing designs onto figure templates	Draw two different designs of each of the following : dresses, skirts, tops, pants and jackets	3.55	0.50	3.62	0.51	3.51	0.58	3.52	0.57	0.20	0.81	NS
21	Draw two different designs of each of the following : dresses, skirts, tops, pants and jackets	Draw three different designs of each of the following accessories- hats, handbags, shoes and boots	3.57	0.58	3.75	0.46	3.64	0.53	3.64	0.53	0.49	0.61	NS
22	Draw three different designs of each of the following accessories- hats, handbags, shoes and boots	Draw four different	3.43	0.62	3.62	0.51	3.43	0.61	3.43	0.61	0.37	0.69	NS
23	Draw four different		3.50	0.54	3.62	0.51	3.45	0.60	3.45	0.60	0.44	0.63	NS

24	jewelries (necklaces, bangles, earrings) Identify design portfolios, contents and layout	3.39	0.68	3.62	0.51	3.44	0.66	3.44	0.66	0.44	0.64	NS
25	Plan and execute a design presentation	3.36	0.67	3.50	0.53	3.33	0.80	3.33	0.80	0.21	0.80	NS
26	Evaluate design presentations	3.41	0.74	3.50	0.53	3.49	0.61	3.48	0.61	0.37	0.68	NS

Key: N1= 46 Home Economics lecturers; N2= 8Fine and Applied Arts lecturers; N3=805 Clothing production experts

SD= Standard Deviation; S= Significant; NS = Not significant \bar{X}_1 = Home Economics Lecturers (HEL); \bar{X}_2 =

Fine and Applied Arts lecturers (FAAL); \bar{X}_3 = Clothing Production experts (CPE); Total respondents =859;

XG= Grand mean. F is significant at Sig of F \leq 0.05, F value= ANOVA

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) reveals that there are no significant differences in the mean ratings of responses of Clothing and Textiles lecturers (CTL), Fine and Applied Arts lecturers (FAAL) and Clothing Production Experts (CPE) twenty-five items. This implies that the null hypothesis was accepted in these twenty-five items. However, item 17 recorded F values that are greater than significance of F at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there were significant differences among the respondents with respect to their opinions on drawing any five different clothing designs and accessories for manufacture as a guideline for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration. The implication is that the respondents have different opinions in that guideline for assessing achievement of objectives. In this regard, the null hypothesis was rejected for item 17.

Occupational Home Economics curriculum is planned and developed on the basis of knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for successful employment in particular jobs. These objectives are in line with what Arubayi (2003) recorded that the goal of teaching Clothing and Textiles is to help learners acquire knowledge, skills and techniques for meeting personal and societal clothing needs. The success of Clothing and Textiles business of Home Economics entrepreneurs depends on the training program in institutions. Home Economics students are supposed to learn practical skills which would enable them get jobs in industries or other formal sectors of the economy. Hence, self-reliance and income generation activities are stressed in the study of Clothing and Textiles.

Fashion Illustration plays a significant role in the manufacturing and marketing of clothing, textiles and accessories. Fashion illustration is a very important part of fashion

designing (Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009; Wolfe, 1993). The fashion business works through a network of organizations, each having its own function. The company involved at each stage need to categories the product visually and describe it, either as part of the production or marketing process. This suggests a need for different types of drawing and for special illustrative skills (Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009). The interdisciplinary perspective of Clothing and Textiles in tertiary institutions could play a key role in generating new knowledge needed to sustain education, train leaders, designers, marketers, entrepreneurs and teachers of tomorrow, communicating the knowledge to decision-makers, policy makers and the public at large (Mastamet-Mason, 2012). Fashion illustration is the communication of fashion that originates with illustration, drawing and painting. Fashion illustration is a form of stylized drawing; it seeks to communicate not only an artistic representation, but a sense of style. It is usually commissioned for reproduction in fashion magazine as one part of an editorial feature or for the purpose of advertising and promoting fashion makers, fashion boutiques and department stores (Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009).

Sketching or illustrate designing is a skill drawn with the assist of number of lines and the design is produced with the help of lines and strokes. However, it differs from drawing. The focus in fashion is to illustrate the fashion facts or croquis used for draping the clothes. Sketching is the foundation of making original pieces of work in fashion network. It has been shown that fashion illustration begins with the sketching of a croquis followed by the extra notation of the garment and also a technological representation of the garment before it is produced. Designers usually sketch out their thoughts and impressions in notebooks before they create (Udale & Sorger, 2006).

The findings of the study showed that all the 26 evaluation guidelines determined in the study were adequate for assessing achievement of fashion illustration objectives. They include drawing children's, women's and men's proportions and body shape, clothing, accessories, and fashion figure proportions among others. Evaluation guidelines determined in this study also include developing two free hand design projects for presentation, drawing any four different clothing designs and for promotion, drawing any five different clothing designs and accessories for manufacture, producing any two fashion illustration articles for advertising and education. Other guidelines include planning and executing a design presentation as well as evaluating design presentations. There was no significant difference in the mean responses of Home Economics lecturers (HEL), Fine and Applied Arts lecturers (FAAL) and Clothing Production experts (CPE) in twenty five out of twenty-six evaluation guidelines. This implies that the null hypothesis was accepted in these guidelines. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the mean responses of the HEL, FAAL, and CPE on these guidelines for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration within the Home Economics curriculum.

However, there was significant difference among the respondents with respect to their opinions on drawing any five different clothing designs for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration. The implication is that the respondents have different opinions in that guideline for assessing achievement of objectives. In this regard, the null hypothesis was rejected for that guideline. Illustration plays an important role in the manufacturing and marketing of fashion clothing and accessories. The fashion business works through a network of organizations, each having its own function. The company involved at each stage need to categorize the product visually and describe it, either as part of the

production or marketing process. This suggests a need for different types of drawing and for special illustrative skills (Mckelvey & Munslow, 2009). It has been reported that the traditional work of portraying fashionable styles in magazines and newspapers has been overshadowed by photography during the second half of the 20th century. Although illustration appears to be more hidden from public view, yet it is still used extensively in the commercial development of a garment or product. Illustration is an integral part of designing. It requires tremendous practice in order to create personal and professional fashion portfolios for the designers and fashion industries. Expertise in various illustration techniques namely fashion sketching, drawing, painting, and the use of graphics is needed.

Similarly, Wolfe (1993) recorded that fashion illustrators draw garments that have been designed and produced by others. Illustrators try to show the good features of apparel in order to promote and sell them. Fashion illustrators work in retail stores, pattern companies, and advertising agencies. In addition to these, design or display studios, textile and apparel manufacturers as well as media industries that produce magazines use fashion illustrators. However, when illustration is done for a pattern company, emphasis is given to seams and to trimming details of the garment. The purpose is to give the garment maker an idea of the construction required. Fashion illustrators who work for fashion magazines or trade publications usually point out trends or garment features being described by fashion writers. Also, for retailing and advertising uses, the illustrator should be able to get the attention of viewers such that they will desire strongly to buy what is shown. However, the amount of pay depends on the person's talent as well as the size or type of industry.

According to Mckelvey and Munslow (2009) fashion illustrations were used for features, covers and advertising in publications. It is important to remark that the use of fashion illustration in commercial art has changed throughout the latter part of 20th century from that of an illustration of an existing garment, to the communication and promotion of garments which are yet to be produced. Fashion illustrators are specialists that create eye catching fashion illustrations. Similarly, (Turnpenny, 1981; Burke, 2006) reported that fashion illustrators and fashion sketch artists illustrate the work of fashion designers in both hand sketches and electronic designs for magazine advertisements, departmental stores, commercials, sales brochures, direct-mail catalogs, and more.

Besides, Mckelvey (2006) documented that fashion illustration is used in the fashion industry to show information in a number of areas which include:

- A mood or feeling that is relevant to current fashion.
- To show a 'total look' including the styling of the pose, face, hair, hands and feet as well as the garment design.
- The proportion and use of colour within an outfit/garment.
- The proportion and use of fabric combinations.
- The proportion of detail in comparison to other garments in the outfit.
- The balance of a collection of garments on a number of figures.

Generally, fashion illustration is used in these two broad areas:

- *Drawing for Promotion-illustrating and promoting new styles*: Drawings are produced either to predict or promote products for forthcoming trends. The two groups of illustration prediction are as follows:

- *Drawings to illustrate themes, influences and directional looks*. These appear to be the most

contemporary of modern illustrative styles which usually has enough detail to convey the style appropriately. Technical, highly detailed working drawings of garments, accessories and fabrics. It is necessary to remark that specification drawings (including measurements) are by some fashion companies. However, fashion illustration features in advertising and editorial. Here freedom of expression can be exercised freely by graphic designers or general illustrators (Mckelvey, 2006).

- *Drawing for Manufacture- by creating 'blue prints' and specification:* It has been indicated that 'working' drawings are used for manufacture. This relates to the standard of communicating garment designs in the industry. It is used in manufacturing to inform designers, pattern cutters, buyers, merchandisers, lay planners, machinists and other people who may be involved in the production of garments, about specific designs. However, working drawings need to be clear. It is important to adapt styles to market requirement (Mckelvey, 2006).

Evaluation in Wheeler's model is not terminal. Findings from the evaluation are fed back into the objectives and the goals, which influence other stages. It is important to remark that evaluation in the current research is not terminal. Findings from the validated draft Fashion Illustration Curriculum were used in the revision of the final copy of the fashion illustration curriculum.

4. Conclusion

The study has determined evaluation guidelines for assessing students' achievement of the Fashion Illustration objectives within the Clothing and Textiles curriculum of Home Economics Education in universities in Nigeria. The findings of the study showed that all the 26 evaluation guidelines determined in the study were adequate for assessing achievement of fashion illustration objectives. They include drawing children's, women's and men's proportions and body shape, clothing, accessories, fashion figure proportions among others. Evaluation guidelines determined in this study also include developing two free hand design projects for presentation, drawing any four different clothing designs and for promotion, drawing any five different clothing designs and accessories for manufacture, producing any two fashion illustration articles for advertising and education. Other guidelines include planning and executing a design presentation as well as evaluating design presentations. There was no significant difference in the mean responses of Home Economics lecturers (HEL), Fine and Applied Arts lecturers (FAAL) and Clothing Production experts (CPE) in twenty five out of twenty-six evaluation guidelines. This implies that the null hypothesis was accepted in these guidelines. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the mean responses of the HEL, FAAL, CPE on these guidelines for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration within the Home Economics curriculum. There was significant difference among the respondents with respect to their opinions on drawing any five different clothing designs for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration. The implication is that the respondents have different opinions in that guideline for assessing achievement of objectives. In this regard, the null hypothesis was rejected for that guideline. The evaluation guidelines for assessing achievement of objectives of fashion illustration are adequate and should therefore be utilized. Based on the findings of the research the study recommended that Curriculum planners (National Universities Commission) and administrators should utilize the evaluation

techniques determined in this study in their review of the current Home Economics programs in Nigerian universities such that their challenging curriculum will prepare students for realistic employment.

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Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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Data Availability Statement

The original contributors presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the author.

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